

Synthesis and oil displacement experiment on sulfobetaine-type fluorocarbon surfactant system

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Abstract : Sulfobetaine-type fluorocarbon surfactant (FS) was synthesized by reaction of *N*-[3-(dimethylamino)propyl]-perfluoroalkyl sulfonamide (NFA) with 2-hydroxy-3-chloropropyl sodium in an alkaline environment. As indicated by the foam performance tests, FS has the optimal foaming and foam stability at the concentration of 0.2 wt%. The oil displacement experiments in sand-packed tube and numerical simulation methods were conducted with the binary foam-complex flooding system including FS (0.2 wt%) + hydrolyzed polyacryamide (HPAM 1000 mg/L) and N₂ in alternating injection slugs. The results showed that the binary foam-complex flooding system could enhance oil recovery by 32.06% over the water flooding; the ultimate oil recovery was up to 76.58%. A mechanistic simulation study has been developed by the CMG-STARs simulator with matching the oil recovery in comparison with laboratory data. The simulation data fit well with tests data in sand-pack tube. HPAM can improve the mobility ratio of the surfactant to crude oil, thicken the flooding medium and increase the sweep volume. Meanwhile, FS can emulsify crude oil and increase the viscosity of the flooding system which can in turn increase the washing oil efficiency. The binary foam-complex flooding system can greatly enhance oil recovery after water flooding. Therefore, FS and its complex system have great potential application and broad prospect to enhance oil recovery in oil fields.

Keywords : Fluorocarbon surfactant, hydrolyzed polyacryamide (HPAM), synthesis, foaming, oil displacement, numerical simulation.

Introduction

Surfactant, even at the extremely low concentration, can apparently reduce the surface tension of the solvent. As an important special surfactant, fluorocarbon surfactant (FS) has currently the highest surface activity, which is better in the temperature resistance and has the chemical stability than other surfactants¹. FS, entitled the “Industrial Monosodium Glutamate”, has a wide range of applications in a lot of technical and economic fields, such as petroleum, firefighting, chemistry, and rubber manufacturing^{1,2}.

The mixtures of the surfactants with the high-molecular water-soluble polymer would have much better effects than before^{2,3}. In the chemical flooding of the oil fields, it's essential to use surfactant for surfactant flooding, complex flooding and foam flooding. The mixed system of FS has abilities of higher temperature resis-

tance, higher salinity and higher acidity, as well as the better foam properties than others⁴. The surfactant plays an important role in enhancing oil recovery (EOR)^{1,3-5}. Therefore, FS has great potential application potential and broad prospect in EOR area^{1,6}.

In recent years, many experts have made a lot of researches in the development and the synthesis of FS and also have achieved great progress after the first occurrence of FS in 1951. Abe *et al.*⁷ researched the surface activity of the C₆H₅CF(CF₃)O[CF₂CF(CF₃)O]_mC₃F₇ with different ether linkages, which showed it is particularly effective in reducing the surface tension. Sawada *et al.*^{8,9} prepared the perfluorinated propyl- and fluoroalkylated 4-vinylpyridinium chloride oligomers, and the fluoroalkylated allyl- and diallylammonium chloride oligomers, which can reduce the surface tension by 10 mN/m. Guittard *et al.*¹⁰ synthesized the nonionic surfactants

of the type polyoxyethylated monomethylated and containing a fluorinated tail from 2-(F-alkyl) ethylamines. These compounds are also effective to reduce the surface tension as nonionic fluorinated surfactants. Mao *et al.*¹¹ and Kondo *et al.*¹² synthesized two fluorine alkyl containing sulfonic acid group fluorocarbon surfactants with the material of perfluorinated alkyl alcohols, oxalic acid anhydride and so on, which can reduce the critical micelle concentration (CMC). Stoilov discovered that the volatile vapors of fluorocarbon substances such as C₆F₁₄, C₈F₁₈ and C₁₀F₁₈ have surface active properties¹³. Meanwhile, many liquids could change their surface tensions at the range of 10–30% by contacting with C₈F₁₈ vapor at room temperature. Zhao and He introduced non-surface active organic ammonium salts into the sodium perfluorooctanoate to synthesize the sodium perfluorooctanoate-trimethylamine hydrochloride, which showed that the surface activity can greatly increase by adding non-surface active organic ammonium salts. The more the amount of the organic ammonium salts are, the more the surface activity increases, which is suitable for practical applications¹⁴. Rodríguez *et al.* developed the phosphocholine-based fluorinated surfactants which showed that the novel fluorinated surfactants perform high surface activity not only in water but also in organic solvents such as *m*-xylene and methanol, especially at low pH values¹⁵. Eastoe *et al.* synthesized four kinds of non-ionic surfactants in order to research their surface adsorption and micellization properties¹⁶. A strong structure-activity relationship was observed, and the surface tension could be reduced by 9 mN/m. Ngo *et al.* synthesized a series of perfluorinated cationic surfactants in order to research their aggregation and surface activity. They discovered that FS can create layered spherical oil and gas accumulation zone, and their CMC and oil/water interfacial tension are lower than those of the hydrocarbon surfactants¹⁷.

Although FS has an excellent surface activity, it is much more expensive, which restricts its applications in EOR area¹⁸. However, mixing FS and hydrocarbon surfactants (e.g. A-olefin sulfonate (AOS)) or other poly-

mers (e.g. hydrolyzed polyacryamide (HPAM), polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP), and hydroxyethyl cellulose (HEC)) can not only achieve much higher surface activity, but also can reduce the cost in applications. The complex flooding in EOR processes refers to the chemical flooding combining two or more chemical components^{19,20}. The polymer-assisted surfactants are defined as the thickness of surfactant flooding or the surfactant reinforced polymer flooding^{21–23}. In recent years, there has been a lot of useful work in the aspect of mixture to research the mixed system done by surfactants experts^{24–29}.

Binary foam-complex flooding technology (e.g. polymer and surfactant) is a mature flooding technology in EOR. Combining the foam system with the advantage of “emphasize” and the binary complex system with the asset of “strong washing oil” can form the property of “emphasize the strong washing oil” when mixing the surfactants with the high-molecular polymers, especially with the soluble polymers (e.g. HPAM)³⁰. Binary foam-complex flooding technology can not only control the oil-water mobility ratio and greatly increase oil recovery, but also reduce the damage to the environment. Meanwhile, the technology can be made full use for other fields in the reservoir development such as well drilling, profile control, water plugging, fracturing and acidizing, and so on^{31,32}.

Recently, many oil fields have entered the middle and extra-high water cut period in the world. It is essential to develop these oil fields under the severe conditions, such as extra-high water cut, high salt, high temperature, low permeability, and so on. Therefore, there are more and more high demands and standards to the surfactants.

However, to the best of our knowledge, aimed at surfactants, previous research mainly focused on the lab evaluation for special properties, failing to consider it as a good oil displacement system to further enhance oil recovery. In addition, the current existing surfactants have many kinds of disadvantages, such as salt sensitive, poor stability to temperature, instability of foam properties, etc.³³. Fluorine-containing surfactants have good proper-

ties of high surface activity, thermal resistance, salt tolerance, acid/alkali resistance, chemical stability and good foam performance, etc., which can meet the needs under the harsh conditions to enhance oil recovery in oil fields^{34,35}.

For its potential use in EOR area, we synthesized the sulfobetaine-type fluorocarbon surfactant by reaction of *N*-[3-(dimethylamino)-propyl]-perfluoroalkyl sulfonamide (NFA) with 2-hydroxy-3-chloropropyl sodium in an alkaline environment. It also has good thermal resistance, salt tolerance, and acid/alkali resistance properties^{36,37}. Moreover, its foaming properties and stabling foam properties were measured by Ross-Miles method. The oil displacement experiments in sand-pack tube and simulation methods by CMG-STARS simulator were conducted with the binary foam-complex flooding system including FS (0.2 wt%) + hydrolyzed polyacryamide (HPAM 1000 mg/L) and nitrogen (N₂) in alternating injection slugs. The oil displacement mechanism of the binary foam-complex flooding system was discussed based upon the incremental oil recovery. The results showed that the binary foam-complex flooding system can greatly enhance oil recovery after water flooding. Therefore, FS and its complex system have great potential prospects in EOR, and the binary foam-complex flooding technology is suitable for application after the conventional water or polymer flooding in oil fields.

Experimental

Synthesis of "FS" :

Structure of "FS" :

FS refers to one surfactant of containing the fluorocarbon chain hydrophobic groups, whose hydrogen atoms of the hydrocarbon chains have been displaced by the fluorine in whole or in part. The structure of FS is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Structure of the fluorocarbon surfactant.

The conventional surfactant is made up by one non-polar part R_F (the oil-wet part of the fluorocarbon chain) and one polar part "X" (hydrophilic part). There are four kinds of fluorocarbon surfactants according to the differences of the "X" as same as the conventional hydrocarbon surfactants, which are anionic, cationic, nonionic and amphoteric types of fluorocarbon surfactants. Moreover, based on the different structures of the anionic, there are some kinds of R_FCOO⁻M⁺, R_FSO₃⁻M⁺, R_FOSO₃⁻M⁺, R_FOP(O)O₂²⁻M₂⁺, etc, where, R_F is fluorocarbon hydrophobic group (hydrophilic group), and "M" is inorganic or organic cation.

Instruments and materials :

Instruments : Thermostatic drying oven and electric-heated thermostatic water bath.

Materials : Twice-distilled water; perfluorooctane sulfonyl fluoride (98 wt%), N,N-dimethyl-1,3-propanediamine (organic amine); isopropyl ether (chemically pure), methanol (analytically pure); epoxy chloropropane (analytically pure); isopropanol (analytically pure) and anhydrous sodium carbonate (analytically pure).

Synthesis procedures :

(1) The synthetic of intermediate product of *N*-[3-(dimethylamino)-propyl]-perfluorinated sulfonamide :

- A certain volume of N,N-dimethyl-1,3-propanediamine was measured and dissolved in certain volume of isopropyl ether; the mixtures were poured into a three-neck flask surrounded by the ice-water bath at the temperature of 10 °C.
- A certain volume of perfluorooctane sulfonyl fluoride was measured and dissolved in a proper volume of isopropyl ether; the mixtures were poured slowly into a three-neck flask at the temperature of 10 °C.
- The mixtures were dropped by the dropping funnel. The temperature was adjusted to 60 °C and the mixtures were poured into beakers open for one day after reacting for about 6 h.
- The suction filtration was operated with absolute

ethyl alcohol and the absolute ethyl alcohol was removed by heating and drying.

- The product was obtained and named as N-[3-(dimethylamino)-propyl]-perfluorinated sulfonamide (NFA).

The chemical equation is as follows :

(2) The synthetic of intermediate product of 2-hydroxy-3-chloropropyl sulfonate :

- A certain quality of NaHSO₃ was poured into appropriate solvents (The solvents were mixed by methanol and water, and the ratio of methanol to water = 3 : 7).
- NaHSO₃ was fully dissolved into the solvents with stirring at the temperature of 70 °C.
- Epoxy chloropropane was added and the temperature was adjusted to 85 °C for reacting for about 3 h. And then the product was cooled crystallization and extracted by the solvents (methanol : water = 3 : 7).
- The product was obtained and named as 2-hydroxy-3-chloropropyl sulfonate.

The chemical equation is as follows :

(3) Synthetic of the sulfobetaine-type fluorocarbon surfactant :

- The intermediate product of N-[3-(dimethylamino)-propyl]-perfluorinated sulfonamide (NFA) was dissolved into appropriate isopropanol.
- The mixture was poured into a three-neck flask and dissolved by heating at the temperature of 60 °C.
- A certain volume of 2-hydroxy-3-chloropropyl sulfonate was dissolved into distilled water and poured into the same three-neck flask to heat and to condensate reflux for 6 h at the temperature of 85 °C.

- The reactants were cooled to 50 °C and a certain amount of NaHSO₃ was added. Heating reaction was made for 6 h at the temperature of 85 °C.
- The reactants were poured into the beaker and the liquid was dried and evaporated, which was extracted by using with the acetone. The product was obtained and named as the sulfobetaine-type fluorocarbon surfactant (FS).

The chemical equation is as follows :

Oil displacement experiment of binary foam-complex flooding system :

Materials and conditions :

- (1) Dewatered crude oil (its viscosity is 920 mPa·s at 50 °C and 2060 mPa·s at room temperature, respectively) was from Daqing Oilfield, China.
- (2) Water was distilled water.
- (3) Binary foam-complex flooding system was composed by FS (0.2 wt%) + 1000 mg/L HPAM (molecular weight 10 million).
- (4) Experimental gas was high-pressure N₂ (nitrogen).
- (5) The property parameters of the sand-pack tube are as follows : radius is 3.0 cm, length is 60 cm, permeability is 370.6 × 10⁻³ um² and porosity is 24.5%.
- (6) The experimental pressure and temperature were 0.1 MPa and 50 °C, respectively.

Experimental device :

The key instruments are composed of HT-α automatic mixing device, thermostat water bath, analytical balance and oven. Fig. 2 shows a schematic drawing of the foam complex flooding experimental device³⁸.

Experimental procedures :

The test procedures were described as follows.

- (1) The formation sand was filled into the sand-pack

Fig. 2. The device of oil displacement experiment.

tube and the sand-pack tube was weighed.

(2) The distilled water was injected at speed of 2 ml/min in order to make the sand-pack tube saturating the water for 4 h. Meanwhile, the permeability was calculated by measuring the pressure across sand-pack tube. The sand-pack tube was weighed and the porosity was calculated.

(3) The saturated-water core was displaced by crude oil at speed of 1 ml/min until there was no water to run; the irreducible water saturation was measured.

(4) Then the core was aged for 24 h at the temperature of 45 °C.

(5) The water flooding experiment was conducted at speed of 0.2 ml/min until the water cut was up to 98% and the oil recovery was calculated.

(6) A certain PV (pore volume) numbers of flooding system (0.3 PV) and nitrogen (0.3 PV) were injected in alternating slugs at a speed of 0.2 ml/min and followed by water flooding until the water cut was up to 98%. Then, the enhanced oil recovery was calculated by the flooding system.

Numerical simulation of binary foam-complex flooding system :

The numerical simulation was performed by injecting the binary foam-complex flooding system in sand-packed tube. CMG-STARs simulator is a compositional reservoir simulator developed by Computer Modeling Group (Canada) which is very useful to model the chemical flooding processes. In this work, a lab procedure is described to build a predictive reservoir model using CMG-STARs

Fig. 3. The grid blocks arranged of 1D core model for the binary foam-complex flooding.

to assist the binary foam-complex flooding system. Fig. 3 shows the grid blocks arranged of 1D core model for the binary foam-complex flooding displacement³⁹.

Some of these assumptions such as well spacing, simulation conditions and other simulation parameters were based on the sand-packed tube as follows.

(1) A basic numerical simulation model was developed first and used in the water flooding. Changes were then made to this model and used in modeling alternating injection FS/HPAM + N₂ flooding after the water flooding. Then following water flooding were carried out.

(2) The fluid data was described with 3 phases and 5 chemical components : water, FS and polymer (HPAM) defined in the aqueous phase, dead oil defined in the oleic phase, and N₂ defined in the gaseous phase.

(3) The sand-packed tube model (60×1×1 grids) (length : 30 cm; diameter : 3.84 cm) was designed to match the sand-packed tube caused by binary foam-complex flooding system.

(4) A 2-spot well spacing was used with one producer and one injector placed on opposite of the core. The injector and the producer were placed in the grid (1, 1, 1) and (60, 1, 1), respectively. Both wells were penetrated in the grid blocks in vertical (Z) direction.

(5) The sand-packed tube was homogeneous, horizontal and equal thickness.

(6) The inner boundary condition of the injector had constant injecting rate and the outer boundary condition of the producer had constant bottomhole flow pressure (0.1 Mpa). The initial condition had the constant pressure (0.1 Mpa) according to the experimental core flooding tests condition.

(7) The PVT analysis, the formation volume factor, the fluid compressibility, the relative permeability for oil-water systems (intermediate wettability rocks) and other relative parameters referred to the actual data in Daqing Oilfield, China.

(8) When the water cut (f_w) of the production liquid went to 98%, the simulator was terminated just like core flooding tests becoming stable as steady state conditions.

Results and discussion

Analysis of infrared spectroscopy :

The IR (infrared) spectroscopy of FS is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. IR spectrum of FS.

There were the symmetric stretching vibration bands of the $-CF_2$ near 558 cm^{-1} , asymmetric stretching vibration bands of the $-CF_2$ near 1150 cm^{-1} and 1240 cm^{-1} , stretching vibration bands of the $-SO_3^{2-}$ near 1060 cm^{-1} , absorption bands of the C-C near the 1515 cm^{-1} and stretching vibration absorption bands of the $-O-H$ near 3490 cm^{-1} .

The IR spectrum result shows that the reactions occurred between the 2-hydroxy-3-chloropropyl sulfonate and the intermediate product of NFA. As a result, the sulfonic root was introduced.

Foam performance :

The different concentrations were prepared with 0.01,

0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 and 0.4 wt% of FS, respectively. After FS was poured into 1000 ml-cylinder, the different foaming volumes (ml) were respectively recorded at 0, 3, 5, 30 min with Ross-Miles method in order to evaluate the foaming properties and stabling foam properties. Fig. 5 shows the effect of FS concentration on the foam properties.

Fig. 5. Effect of FS concentration on the foam properties.

From Fig. 5, the foaming properties of the FS were much poorer at lower concentrations. It could produce a relative larger foam volume at the concentration of 0.2 wt%. The foaming volume of FS also increased with the increase of the concentration which illustrated that it had the good foaming properties. The foam life of the foaming agent increased with the increase of the concentration and the foaming volume kept for a long time. When the foaming volume was up to a certain value, it maintained the stability for a long period of time which explained the foam stability was better. When the concentration exceeded 0.2%, the foaming properties and the foam stability properties could not increase by a large margin with the increase of the concentration, which illustrated that the molecule of FS in the solution surface was close to saturation state and the surface activity was close to the maximum. As indicated by the tests, FS has the optimal foaming and foam stability at the mass fraction of 0.2 wt%.

Effect of oil displacement :

Results of oil displacement experiment :

HPAM is a very common flooding oil polymer. It is used extensively in the oil field. By the binary surfactant-polymer complex flooding, the polymer can change the mobility ratio, thicken the viscosity, reduce the injected rate of the surfactant and its consumption, and increase the stability of oil-in-water emulsion, which will result in largely increasing the sweep efficiency and washing oil capacity. Based on earlier optimized results, the experimental injected binary foam-complex flooding system was replicated by FS (0.2 wt%) +1000 mg/L HPAM (molecular weight 10 million) + N₂ (frother agent), which has the maximum foaming volume and exhibits a relatively better performance in oil displacement.

The oil displacement FS/HPAM system (0.35 PV) and nitrogen (0.35 PV) were injected in alternating slugs. Table 1 lists the comparative results by the binary foam-complex flooding system and water flooding. From Table 1, the oil recovery was only 44.53% by water flooding. While, it was increased by 32.06% after FS/HPAM system (0.35 PV) and nitrogen (0.35 PV) were injected in alternating slugs. The ultimate oil recovery was up to 76.58%.

Table 1. Comparative results of oil displacement experiment in sand-pack tube

Water flooding	Binary foam-complex flooding system			Complex effects
	FS/HPAM	N ₂	EOR	
EOR (%)	(PV)	(PV)	(%)	EOR (%)
44.53	0.35	0.35	32.06	76.58

The black dots of Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 represent respectively the relationships between the oil recovery and injection pressure gradient with different injection volume numbers.

From Fig. 6, the water flooding oil recovery was only 44.53%. The oil recovery increased to 76.58% and the complex recovery increased by 32.06% after injecting the slug of 0.35 PV flooding system and 0.35 PV N₂. From the different oil recovery curves, we can see the

Fig. 6. The relationship between the oil recovery and injection volume.

Fig. 7. The relationship between injection pressure gradient and injection volume.

complex recovery has obvious rising trend in the basic of the water flooding. There is a non-smooth wave during the rising. This is because there are different flooding systems with different flooding mechanisms. The complex oil recovery curve has obvious advancement at the switched injection point over the water flooding.

From Fig. 7, when the sand-filled pipe saturated oil was conducted by water flooding, the injection-production pressure difference immediately decreased. As a result, the residual oil was hardly moved by water. After the system was switched to inject the slug of the binary foam-complex flooding system and N₂, the injection-production pressure difference immediately increased and recovered to the original pressure difference to make the residual oil to flow. When the binary foam-complex flood-

ing finished and was switched the conventional water flooding, the injection-production pressure difference decreased again. The further conventional water flooding had the residual pressure difference, which can continue to flood the residual oil in the sand-filled pipe.

Results of numerical simulation :

The solid lines of Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 represent respectively the relationships between the oil recovery and injection pressure gradient with different injection volume numbers by numerical simulation methods.

From Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, the comparison shows that there is a better agreement between the experimental flooding tests data and the simulation data.

Different flooding systems have the different flooding mechanisms. The good synergistic effect, which resulted from the electrostatic force and hydrogen-bond action as well as the ion-dipole interaction between the surfactant polar head and the polymer polar part between the HPAM (strong hydrolysis) and amphoteric fluorocarbon surfactant, can remarkably enhance oil recovery. Meanwhile, FS/HPAM system can form the stable foam after N₂ injection.

On the one hand, HPAM can improve the mobility ratio, thicken the flooding system, reduce the spread and consumption of the surfactant, and thereby increase the sweep volume. On the other hand, FS can emulsify crude oil, increase the viscosity of flooding system, decrease the surface tension between the polymers and crude oil, and thereby increase the washing oil efficiency^{21,22}. FS and its binary foam-complex flooding system have great potential prospect in the tertiary oil recovery in oil fields.

Conclusions

Based on the present work, the following conclusions can be drawn :

- (1) The sulfobetaine-type fluorocarbon surfactant (FS) was synthesized in the laboratory by reaction of NFA with 2-hydroxy-3-chloropropyl sodium in an alkaline environment.
- (2) As indicated by the tests, FS has the optimal foaming and foam stability at the concentration of 0.2

wt%.

- (3) The oil displacement experiments and numerical simulation methods were conducted with the binary foam-complex flooding system including FS (0.2 wt%), HPAM (1000 mg/L) and N₂ in alternating slugs injected, which could enhance oil recovery by 32.06% over the water flooding, and the ultimate oil recovery is up to 76.58%.
- (4) HPAM can improve the mobility ratio, thicken the viscosity, and increase the sweep volume. FS can emulsify crude oil and increase the viscosity of the flooding system, which in turn increases the washing oil efficiency.
- (5) The binary foam-complex flooding system could greatly enhance oil recovery after water flooding. Results have shown that FS and its binary foam-complex flooding system have great prospect in EOR processes in the future.

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References

1. I. Hisamoto, C. Maeda, T. Esaka and M. Nishiwaki. U.S. Patent, 4303534, 1981.
2. C. Wolf, K. Bressel, M. Drechsler and M. Gradzielski, *Langmuir*, 2009, **25**, 11358.
3. A. Song, S. Dong, J. Hao, W. Liu, G. Xu and H. Wang, *J. Fluorine Chem.*, 2005, **126**, 1266.
4. Y. Kondo, E. Yokochi, S. Mizumura and N. Yoshino, *J. Fluorine Chem.*, 1998, **91**, 147.
5. C. A. McPhee, A. D. H. Tehrania and R. P. S. Jolly, SPE17360-MS, 1988, 433.
6. X. C. Ma and Y. F. Cao, *Dalian Ins. of Light Ind.*, 1997, **16**, 6.

7. M. Abe, K. Morikawa, K. Ogino, H. Sawada, T. Matsumoto and M. Nakayama, *Langmuir*, 1992, **8**, 763.
8. H. Sawada, K. I. Tanba, M. Oue, T. Kawase, Y. Hayakawa, M. Mitani and Y. Moriya. *Polym.*, 1995, **36**, 2103.
9. H. Sawada, A. Wake, M. Oue, T. Kawase, Y. Hayakawa, Y. Minoshima and M. Mitani, *J. Colloid and Interf. Sci.*, 1996, **178**, 379.
10. F. Guittard, E. T. de Givenchy and A. Cambon, *J. Colloid and Interf. Sci.*, 1996, **177**, 101.
11. S. Q. Mao, M. F. Tang and C. Gu. *Organo-fluorine Ind.*, 1996, **11**, 1.
12. Y. Kondo, E. Yokochi, S. Mizumura and N. Yoshino, *J. Fluorine Chem.*, 1998, **91**, 147.
13. Y. Y. Stoilov, *Langmuir*, 1998, **14**, 5685.
14. B. Y. Zhu, G. X. Zhao and S. G. He, *China Surf. Detergen & Cosmetics*, 1998, **10**, 1.
15. C. Rodríguez, H. Kunieda, Y. Noguch and T. Nakaya, *J. Colloid and Interf. Sci.*, 2001, **242**, 255.
16. J. Eastoe, A. Paul, A. Rankin, R. Wat, J. Penfold and J. R. Webster, *Langmuir*, 2001, **17**, 7873.
17. T. H. V. Ngo, C. Damas, R. Naejus and R. Coudert. *J. Fluorine Chem.*, 2010, **131**, 704.
18. K. Sakai, M. Kaji, Y. Takamatsu, K. Tsuchiya, K. Torigoe, K. Tsubone and M. Abe, *Colloids and Surfaces (A)*, 2009, **333**, 26.
19. M. Baviere, P. Glenat, V. Plazanet and J. Labrid, *SPE Res. Eng.*, 1995, **10**, 187.
20. P. C. Liu, C. Wang and Y. L. Wang, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2016, **93**, 449.
21. T. Maldal, E. Gilje, R. Kristensen, T. Karstad, A. Nordbotten, B. E. R. Schilling and O. Vikane, *SPE Res. Eval. Eng.*, 1998, **1**, 161.
22. T. Austad, I. Fjelde, K. Veggeland and K. Taugbøl, *J. Pet. Sci. Eng.*, 1994, **110**, 255.
23. J. Bock, P. L. Valint and S. J. Pace, U.S. Patent, 4702319, 1987.
24. M. Villeneuve, T. Nomura, H. Matsuki, S. Kaneshina and M. Aratono, *J. Colloid and Interf. Sci.*, 2001, **234**, 127.
25. K. Stähler, J. Selb and F. Candau, *Langmuir*, 1999, **15**, 7565.
26. A. Ito, H. Sakai, Y. Kondo, N. Yoshino and M. Abe, *Langmuir*, 1996, **12**, 5768.
27. R. Oda, I. Huc, D. Danino and Y. Talmon, *Langmuir*, 2000, **16**, 9759.
28. P. Barthélémy, V. Tomao, J. Selb, Y. Chaudier and B. Pucci, *Langmuir*, 2002, **18**, 2557.
29. Y. Chaudier, P. Barthélémy and B. Pucci, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2001, **42**, 3583.
30. L. M. Zhang, S. J. Huang and D. Q. Chen, *Appl. Chem.*, 1998, **10**, 115.
31. Z. K. Liu and J. H. Min, *Oil and Gas Recovery Techno.*, 1996, **3**, 23.
32. M. M. Wang, Z. J. Chang, H. L. Xi, Y. J. Zuo, H. Z. Liu and W. J. Li, *Chem. Eng. Prog.*, 2005, **24**, 723.
33. M. Baviere, P. Glenat, V. Plazanet and J. Labrid, *SPE Res. Eng.*, 1995, **10**, 187.
34. P. Barthélémy, V. Tomao, J. Selb, Y. Chaudier and B. Pucci, *Langmuir*, 2002, **18**, 2557.
35. Y. Chaudier, P. Barthélémy and B. Pucci, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2001, **42**, 3583.
36. Y. L. Wang, J. J. Zheng and X. T. Zhao, *J. Shandong Normal University*, 2009, **2**, 63.
37. Y. L. Wang, J. J. Zheng, X. T. Zhao, Y. F. Wang and Y. L. Chang, *Bulletin of the Chinese Ceramic Soc.*, 2010, **29**, 314.
38. P. C. Liu, Y. B. Wu and X. L. Li, *Fuel*, 2013, **111**, 12.
39. P. C. Liu and X. K. Zhang, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, 2015, **40**, 12849.

